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Case Study

Liver Cirrhosis Reversed: Hope with Neo Ayurveda's Herbal Protocol : A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

This case study highlights the efficacy of Neo Ayurveda's 100% herbal treatment protocol in reversing advanced-stage liver cirrhosis. The author, Dr. S.M. Raju, an agricultural science expert, began exploring natural remedies after healing himself from rheumatoid arthritis and successfully treating his father, mother, and son for various chronic and life-threatening conditions. His journey led to the development of Neo Ayurveda, a holistic system that leverages prebiotics, probiotics, and herbal extracts to activate gut microbes and release essential enzymes, thereby addressing the nutritional needs of the body's organs. In this study, a 64-year-old male patient diagnosed with fifth-stage liver cirrhosis, diabetes, hypertension, and hypothyroidism was treated with the Neo Ayurveda herbal protocol. The patient discontinued all allopathic medications and adhered to a strict dietary regimen, including prebiotic foods, herbal supplements, and carefully defined dietary restrictions. Within one week of treatment, the patient experienced significant symptomatic relief, including the resolution of abdominal discomfort, lower limb pain, and dysphagia. After one month, the patient's liver function markers improved significantly, with reductions in HbA1c, blood glucose levels, ALP, GGT, and blood pressure. Furthermore, the patient lost 7 kg and reported overall health improvement. This case suggests that the Neo Ayurveda protocol may offer an effective alternative to liver transplantation by promoting liver regeneration and improving metabolic health. Further clinical studies are needed to validate these findings and explore the long-term safety and efficacy of this treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Liver cirrhosis is a progressive disease characterized by the replacement of healthy liver tissue with scar tissue (fibrosis), leading to the deterioration of liver function. Commonly

associated with chronic conditions such as alcoholic liver disease and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), cirrhosis is often considered irreversible, particularly in its

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advanced stages, and is typically managed through lifestyle changes, pharmacotherapy, and in severe cases, liver transplantation. However, the success of liver transplantation is not guaranteed, and the procedure is often prohibitively expensive and associated with significant risks. In recent years, there has been growing interest in integrative and alternative therapies for chronic liver conditions, particularly those grounded in traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda. Neo Ayurveda, a system developed by Dr. S.M. Raju, blends Ayurvedic principles with modern insights into gut health, prebiotics, and probiotics to promote organ regeneration and function. Rooted in the principle of using food as medicine, Neo Ayurveda focuses on restoring the natural balance of the body's organs by addressing the roles of gut microbes in the activation of essential enzymes and nutrients needed for cellular repair and organ function. Dr. Raju, the founder of Miracle Drinks and the developer of the Neo Ayurveda protocol, was driven to explore alternative therapies after successfully treating himself for rheumatoid arthritis in 1973 and later curing his father of acute renal failure, his mother of asthma and joint pain, and his son of Acute Myeloid Leukemia in 2010. These experiences motivated him to develop and standardize treatment protocols that address the root causes of chronic and so-called "incurable" diseases. The central hypothesis of Neo Ayurveda is that many chronic diseases, including liver cirrhosis, result from an imbalance in the body's internal systems, which can be corrected through targeted dietary interventions and herbal therapies that promote gut-liver axis health. By activating gut microbes and encouraging the release of specific enzymes, this approach aims to restore the natural blood circulation system, even in dysfunctional organs, without the need for invasive procedures like liver transplantation. This case study presents the application of Neo Ayurveda's herbal protocol to a 64-year-old

patient diagnosed with advanced-stage liver cirrhosis. The patient, who was advised to undergo liver transplantation, chose to discontinue all allopathic treatments and adhered to the Neo Ayurveda protocol, which included a strict dietary regimen, herbal supplements, and prebiotic foods. Over a 30-day period, the patient exhibited significant improvements in liver function, metabolic health, and overall well-being, suggesting the potential for this protocol to serve as a viable alternative to conventional treatments for liver cirrhosis.

Patient Information

- Name: C. Nagaraju
- Age: 64
- Date of diagnosis : 25.6.24, medications advised after testing fibro scan on dated 4.7.24 , doctors declared that it is in advance stage and declared that liver transplant is required.
- Date of Neo Ayurveda treatment : 10.7.2024
- Date of Testimony: 6th August 2024

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Case Report:

The patient, C. Nagaraju, a 64-year-old male, presented with a history of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) compounded by obesity. His dietary habits were predominantly non-vegetarian, with a high consumption of red meat. Upon presentation, the patient reported experiencing dyspnoea (shortness of breath), dysphagia (difficulty swallowing), abdominal discomfort, and pain in the lower limbs , no appetite and ascites. Laboratory evaluations and diagnostic imaging revealed the following clinical parameters:

- HbA1c: 7.7% (indicating poorly controlled diabetes)
- Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG): 120 mg/dL
- Postprandial Blood Glucose (PBG): 242 mg/dL

- Average Blood Glucose (eAG): 174 mg/dL
- Blood Pressure: 150/90 mmHg
- Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase (GGT): 78 U/L
- Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP): 381 U/L
- Fibro Scan Results: Mean liver stiffness of 303 kPa ($\pm$ 63.5), consistent with advanced cirrhosis.

Additional findings included congestive gastropathy and the presence of a polyp in the pharynx. Based on these evaluations, the patient was diagnosed with fifth-stage chronic liver disease. He was advised that liver transplantation was the only viable treatment option, though with a guarded prognosis due to the advanced stage of his condition. The patient had been prescribed medications for the management of multiple conditions, including diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and hypothyroidism. However, after learning about the Neo Ayurveda Miracle Drinks protocol from his son, the patient decided to discontinue all allopathic treatments and initiated the Neo Ayurveda treatment protocol on July 10, 2024.

Diagnostic Focus and Assessment:

In June 2024, the patient was diagnosed with fifth-stage liver cirrhosis, along with concurrent diagnoses of diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and hypothyroidism.

Treatment Decision:

On the first day of treatment, the patient discontinued all prescribed allopathic medications as part of his decision to follow the Neo Ayurveda protocol exclusively

Therapeutic intervention –

Standardized Treatment Protocol

The Neo Ayurveda Miracle Drinks treatment protocol is a holistic regimen aimed at addressing liver cirrhosis and associated metabolic conditions in one standardized treatment protocols, where in it take care all other ailments if the patients have like diabetes, chronic kidney diseases, pancreatitis, heart related problems etc. In the system of the

treatment it is not only addresses predominant health issues but also other issues. The key components of the protocol include herbal supplements, prebiotic dietary interventions, certain foods are harmful during the treatment period it should not be taken and certain defined foods should be taken, cereals should be taken less than 25% and 60% leafy vegetables and vegetable preparations with defined pulses and defined method of food should be prepared. This modifications designed to support liver function, detoxification, and metabolic balance.

Therapeutic Intervention

Standardized Treatment Protocol:

The Neo Ayurveda Miracle Drinks treatment protocol is a holistic regimen designed to address liver cirrhosis and associated metabolic conditions. It follows a standardized approach that can also manage other health issues such as diabetes, chronic kidney disease, pancreatitis, and heart-related conditions. The system not only targets predominant health issues but also addresses concurrent conditions.

Key components of the protocol include:

- Herbal supplements
- Prebiotic dietary interventions

Certain foods that are harmful during the treatment period must be avoided, while specific foods are required. The dietary modifications are structured to support liver function, detoxification, and metabolic balance. Cereal intake is restricted to less than 25%, while 60% of the diet should consist of leafy vegetables and vegetable preparations with defined pulses prepared using specified methods.

Dietary Guidelines:

a. Foods restricted during the treatment period:

- Salt intake: Limited to less than 5 grams.
- Oils and fats: All forms should be avoided.
- Milk and dairy products: Avoid all, except curds/yogurt without cream.

- Processed and bakery foods: Foods like cookies and biscuits should be avoided.
 - Pulses: High consumption of pulses should be restricted.
 - Cereals: Coarse grains like millets and minor millets should be avoided.
 - Rice and chapatti: Consumption of more than 25% rice or bread (chapatti/rotti) should be avoided. These cereals contain 14% indigestible protein and 70% carbohydrates, which are not easily digestible.
 - Alcohol, aerated beverages, and fruit juices: These should not be consumed.
 - Red meats: Mutton, beef, pork, and skinned chicken should not be consumed.
- b. Foods recommended during the treatment:**
- Prebiotics: Garlic (3 pieces), 1 inch of sliced ginger, and 1 teaspoon of soaked fenugreek seeds to be consumed once daily.
 - Banana stem juice: Consumed twice daily (50-60 ml each time) to help remove calcareous formations in the arteries and capillaries.
 - Raw vegetable juice: Consumed twice daily (50-60 ml each time) to maintain cholesterol levels, blood thinning, and manage gastric issues.
 - Leached vegetable salad: Should be consumed in limited quantities.
 - Fruits: Any type of fruits or berries in limited quantities, observing potassium levels.
 - Flax drink (with Edemax powder): Consumed twice daily, morning and evening. This drink contains omega-3 and omega-6 essential fatty acids and high amounts of lignans, which aid in detoxifying cells, and regulating the metabolic activity. One portion of the flax diet provides the nutritional equivalent of 100 kg of peanuts in terms of quantum of lignans and omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids. The flax diet should be taken without mixing water.
- Leached cooked leafy vegetables and preparations with 5-10% pulses: More than 60% of the diet should consist of these foods.
 - Cereals: Only rice, wheat, and jowar should be consumed, as they contain low potassium levels and are easily digestible. No more than 25-30% of cereals should be consumed in each meal. Coarse grains with high levels of potassium should be avoided.
 - Fish: Up to 15-20% of baked fish with herbs can be consumed, as it supports regeneration of the kidneys and other organs.
 - Chicken: Baked chicken can be consumed, though it should not constitute more than 5% of the total meal.
 - Mushrooms: Up to 15-20% baked mushrooms with herbs can be consumed to support the regeneration of kidneys and other organs.
 - Spice drink: Can be consumed to help with allergies, fever, cold, and cough.
- c. Treatment protocol with proprietary herbal medicines under Ayurveda and dietary guidelines (defined as health supplements under FSSAI):**
- Morning Protocol:**
1. On an empty stomach, the patient consumes Ayurvedic supplements such as Sugar Care, Gastro Support, and Renal Support, and edemax supplements powder (acts like diuretic medication)
 2. Prebiotic supplements: 2-3 pieces of garlic, ½ cm of fresh ginger, and ½ teaspoon of soaked fenugreek seeds.
 3. 20 minutes of meditation and pranayama: 40 sets of Bhastrika and 20 sets of Anuloma Viloma.
 4. 50 ml of banana stem juice is consumed.
 5. A Flax Diet mixed with ½ teaspoon of Edemax powder, providing omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, is consumed. The

preparation involves grinding 15 grams of raw flax seeds, adding 15 ml of cold-pressed flax oil and 100 ml curd, churning thoroughly to emulsify the oil, and consuming within 15 minutes of preparation.

Afternoon Protocol:

- Pre-lunch supplements include Cardiovascular Support. Lunch follows the defined dietary guidelines.
- Evening Protocol:
- The patient consumes the Flax Diet again as part of the treatment protocol.

Night Protocol:

On an empty stomach, the patient consumes Sugar Care, Gastro Support, and Renal Support. health supplements and edemax supplements powder (acts like diuretic medication)

1. Dinner follows the defined dietary guidelines.

RESULTS

Results After One Week:

Within one week of beginning the Neo Ayurveda Miracle Drinks treatment protocol, the patient experienced a complete resolution of all major physical symptoms. Abdominal pain, lower limb discomfort, dyspnoea (shortness of breath), and dysphagia (difficulty swallowing) subsided. Additionally, the patient reported a significant improvement in appetite and ascites disappeared.

Results After One Month:

After adhering to the treatment protocol for one month, by August 6, 2024, the patient showed significant improvements in both clinical symptoms and laboratory parameters:

- HbA1c: Reduced from 7.7% to 5.5%
- Mean Blood Glucose (e-AG): Reduced from 174 mg/dL to 111 mg/dL
- Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG): Reduced from 120 mg/dL to 91 mg/dL
- Postprandial Blood Glucose (PBG): Reduced from 242 mg/dL to 120 mg/dL

- Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP): Reduced from 381 U/L to 307 U/L
- Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase (GGT): Reduced from 78 U/L to 40 U/L
- Blood Pressure: Normalized to within the healthy range
- Weight: Reduced from 104 kg to 97 kg

All physical symptoms related to liver cirrhosis had resolved, and the patient's overall health showed marked improvement. The patient continues to follow the Neo Ayurveda protocol with sustained benefits, suggesting the effectiveness of this holistic treatment in managing and reversing advanced liver cirrhosis and its related conditions.

DISCUSSION

The Neo Ayurveda protocol, as presented in this case study, demonstrates remarkable potential in managing and possibly reversing advanced-stage liver cirrhosis through non-invasive, natural therapies. The protocol integrates prebiotics, probiotics, and herbal supplements, emphasizing the importance of the gut-liver axis in promoting cellular regeneration and improving metabolic health. The results obtained in this case suggest that the approach may have induced functional recovery in the fibrotic liver, possibly through mechanisms involving the stimulation of gut microbiota and the rebalancing of the body's metabolic processes. The use of prebiotics such as garlic, ginger, and fenugreek likely contributed to this effect by promoting a healthy gut environment, which in turn may have facilitated better nutrient absorption and enzyme activation, essential for liver regeneration.

Dietary and Herbal Interventions

A key component of the Neo Ayurveda protocol is its focus on a carefully structured diet. The prescribed dietary interventions, which included the consumption of raw vegetable juices, banana stem juice, and a flax diet enriched with omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, are likely to have played

a significant role in reducing systemic inflammation. Omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids are known to have anti-inflammatory properties, which may have helped mitigate liver inflammation and promote regeneration of hepatocytes (liver cells). The high fibre and nutrient content of the diet may have also contributed to a reduction in cholesterol and the regulation of blood sugar levels, as evidenced by the patient's significant improvements in HbA1c and other metabolic markers.

MECHANISM OF ACTION

The observed clinical improvements suggest that the Neo Ayurveda protocol operates through several synergistic mechanisms:

- **Improved microvascular circulation:**

The protocol likely improves blood flow at the capillary level, particularly in the liver and other dysfunctional organs. Enhanced circulation would allow for better nutrient delivery to damaged tissues, promoting healing and regeneration.

- **Detoxification:**

The protocol's reliance on natural, plant-based supplements may enhance the body's detoxification processes, particularly in the liver, which is responsible for filtering toxins from the blood. Improved detoxification is essential for restoring normal liver function in cirrhotic patients.

- **Cellular restoration:**

By activating the gut-liver axis, the treatment protocol may have facilitated the production and release of necessary enzymes that support cellular repair and regeneration within the liver. This hypothesis is supported by the observed reduction in liver stiffness as indicated by the patient's Fibro Scan results.

Symptom Resolution and Metabolic Improvements

Within one week of starting the protocol, the patient experienced a complete resolution of his

major physical symptoms, including abdominal pain, lower limb discomfort, dyspnoea, and dysphagia. These improvements suggest that the protocol not only addressed the underlying liver condition but also positively impacted related metabolic conditions, including diabetes and hypertension. After one month of treatment, the patient's significant reduction in HbA1c levels from 7.7% to 5.5% and weight loss of 7 kg reflect a marked improvement in metabolic health. These findings indicate that the Neo Ayurveda protocol may offer a comprehensive solution for managing multiple chronic conditions simultaneously, without the need for invasive treatments such as liver transplantation.

IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This case study demonstrates the potential of Neo Ayurveda as a viable alternative to conventional treatments for liver cirrhosis, particularly for patients who may not have access to or prefer to avoid liver transplantation. However, the findings from this case study, while promising, are preliminary and limited to a single patient. Further clinical trials with larger sample sizes are necessary to confirm the reproducibility and generalizability of these results. Future studies should explore the long-term safety and efficacy of the Neo Ayurveda protocol, as well as its potential for treating other metabolic conditions beyond liver cirrhosis, such as diabetes and chronic kidney disease. The holistic nature of the Neo Ayurveda protocol, combined with its focus on natural, non-invasive treatments, positions it as a promising integrative approach in the treatment of chronic liver diseases. It represents an important step forward in the growing field of integrative medicine, which seeks to combine the best practices of traditional and modern medical systems to provide more comprehensive and patient-centred care.

CONCLUSION

This case study highlights the potential of the Neo Ayurveda – Miracle Drinks treatment protocol in reversing advanced-stage liver cirrhosis, while simultaneously improving other associated metabolic disorders such as diabetes and hypertension. The patient, who was initially advised to undergo a liver transplant, experienced significant improvements in both clinical symptoms and laboratory markers within one month of adhering to the treatment protocol. Notably, the patient's liver function markers, blood glucose levels, and overall metabolic health showed remarkable improvement, along with a resolution of the physical symptoms associated with liver cirrhosis. The results suggest that the Neo Ayurveda protocol, which integrates dietary interventions, probiotics, herbal supplements, and lifestyle modifications, may offer a promising non-invasive alternative to liver transplantation. Its holistic approach addresses not only the primary liver condition but also related metabolic issues, thereby offering a comprehensive and multifaceted treatment option for patients with chronic diseases. However, while the outcomes of this case are promising, it is important to recognize that these findings are based on a single patient. Therefore, further large-scale clinical trials are necessary to validate the efficacy and safety of the Neo Ayurveda protocol in a broader population. Long-term studies will also be crucial in determining the sustainability of the treatment's benefits and its ability to prevent the progression of liver cirrhosis in the long term. The holistic nature of the Neo Ayurveda approach, which combines traditional Ayurvedic principles with

modern insights into gut health and metabolic balance, provides an integrative treatment framework that could significantly improve patient outcomes in chronic liver disease and other metabolic disorders. Moving forward, the potential for this protocol to serve as an alternative to conventional treatment modalities like liver transplantation underscores the need for more research in the field of integrative medicine.

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